

Deliverable Report 7.1

Project Website

Version 3

WP 7
Deliverable 7.1
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IGNITION – Improving **Green** Innovation for the blue revolu**TION**: new tools and opportunities for a more sustainable animal farming is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement: 101084651)

Executive Summary

This Deliverable Report summarizes Deliverable D7.1 – Project website – achieved in the IGNITION project.

The deliverable refers to Task 7.1.1 “External communication development and management”, led by Scitation. The website will be constantly updated information on the activities, results of the project. It will be developed as repository for all stakeholders with information and resources of the project, including advance training content, public deliverables, leaflets and other communication material.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

A professionally designed English-language website (ignition-project.eu) has been built by Scitation in November 2022. It provides information about the project's concepts, main goals, partners involved in the consortium and results, showcasing the project's news, and progress and acting as a communication channel with stakeholders, SMEs, entrepreneurs, industry associations, investors, and the local communities. It will offer downloadable public deliverables (once approved) and results (once they can be publicly disclosed) and will operate as a repository for project information. Promotional material (e.g. leaflet) will be available in digital format as marketing tools for stakeholders, SMEs, etc. It establishes links to social media channels (figure 1) and with other relevant projects/initiatives. It is, thus, an important tool in the Communication and Dissemination of project results (more information will be available in D6.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan).

Populating the website will be the responsibility of the whole consortium, as the Dissemination and Exploitation Board is composed of one responsible element from each partner institution. All partners will be ambassadors of the project and ensure that project news are posted and shared to the combined outreach of all the consortium. The information on the website should always be simple and accessible to all types of public. Scitation will be responsible for the website maintenance.

2. Compliance

The website (ignition-project.eu) was built following the brand guidelines defined in the Brand Book, available in the common folder under '[Ignition – Project Wide](#)' / '[3. Templates & Logos](#)' / '[Ignition - BrandBook \(v.21.12.2022\).pdf](#)'.

It complies with the conditions set out in the GA, including the funding acknowledgement in the footer, which is always visible (figure 1). The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what IGNITION does with any personal data gathered (Figure 1).

Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website.

Figure 1: Banner with funding acknowledgement and privacy policy

To ensure successful promotion of the project, sustaining the interest of the target audience while attracting new users, the website will be continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project. The website will remain active for five years after the end of the project, to serve as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and for promoting the outputs of publicly funded research beyond the project's lifetime.

3. Overview

3.1. Home page

The homepage has a strong branding role (Figure 2) and the latest news are readily presented to the visitor.

Figure 2: Home page overview

3.2. The project

The project webpage provides an overview of the objectives (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Project tab, including the objectives

3.3. Partners

The partner page lists all the institutions in the consortium (Figure 4) and offers a link to the project partners website.

Figure 4: Partners webpage listing the institutions in the consortium

3.4. Work packages

The last page of the website offers an overview of the project structure (Figure 5). Each work package can be selected for more information, including the goals.

Figure 5: Overview of the project structure and interaction between WPs

3.5. News

A news tab was added to website at a later stage (Figure 6). In this tab all news published during the project are visible, from the most recent to the oldest. All partners contribute with news for the website.

Figure 6: news section of the website

3.6. Resources

As the project progresses, many communication and dissemination resources have been created, which required the creation of a new tab, dedicated to resources (Figure 7), including the communication materials, under project overview, videos, publications, infographics and podcasts and webinars.

Figure 7: Webpage where communication and dissemination resources can be found

Document information

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